

WIND VALUE

An Opportunity for Climate Action and for Energy Communities

**End of Life Decisions for Wind Farms:
An Opportunity for Climate Action and for Energy Communities**

**Social Media and Website Report 2: First Journal Paper
Deliverable 1.4**

Report on Month 34/48, December 2024

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Executive Summary

This research project seeks to estimate a financial valuation for onshore wind farms in Ireland. It will develop decision support tools which will assist wind farm managers to decide between decommissioning, repowering and life-extension for the end-of-life of a wind farm. This research will also assist local communities who may be interested in buying part or all of their local wind farm.

A social media channel, Twitter [@windvalue](#) and a website <https://windvalue.ie/> were set up to help to disseminate the output of the project and to facilitate engagement with stakeholders. The principal investigator’s [LinkedIn](#) account proved to be very effective and is formally included in this report. Both the social media, [Twitter / X](#) and [LinkedIn](#), and the project’s [website](#) exceeded their activity targets for publication of the project’s first international peer reviewed paper in [Applied Economics](#) [1]. This report which was planned to coincide with the publication has been delayed to coincide with the 2024 annual report.

1 Introduction

This short deliverable is a report on the social media impact of the publication on 21st July 2024 of Wind Value's first international peer reviewed journal paper, Mikindani, D., O'Brien, J., Leahy, P., & Deeney, P. (2024). **The financial risks from wind turbine failures: A value at risk approach**. Applied Economics, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2024.2380542>. Applied Economics carries an ABS 2 rank, has an impact factor of 1.8 (2023) and is published by Taylor & Francis. The paper is available on open access from the publishers [here](#) , or from University College Cork's Open Research Archive, [CORA](#).

It was found during the project that there was a much greater impact from the publication of [1] on LinkedIn than on the project's Twitter / X account, and so LinkedIn is added to this report.

2 Social Media

As specified in the funding application, the number of Twitter followers will be the metric used to chart the progress of the project's social media outreach. The target for the publication of the first journal paper from the proposal is to have 200 followers on Twitter/X and 400 website visits.

2.1 Twitter X

The Wind Value Twitter/X account attracted 443 followers by 28th December 2024, the target was 200, (see Figure 1). The response to the publication of the paper was somewhat dissappointing on Twitter, but much more enthusiastic on LinkedIn.

Figure 1: Twitter Screenshot 28 December 2024

2.2 LinkedIn

The notification of the paper on the PI's LinkedIn page <https://www.linkedin.com/in/peterdeeney/> attracted a response of 2,693 impressions, (see Figure 2). This was the most successful of the methods used to reach out to the public, researchers and industry.

Figure 2: LinkedIn Screenshot on 28 October 2024

3 Website

3.1 Metrics and Targets

The project website has added some tabs for recent events, notably the second conference and the visit to Tanzania, see Figure 3.

Following the method used for the previous report (Social Media and Website Report 1, Deliverable 1.2, Month 6/48 DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10049074) Webalizer 2.21 was used to track the visits from secure URLs only.

The target set for website visits on the publication of the first paper of the project was 400 visits.

3.2 Results

The number of visits by secure URLs from February 2024 to December 2024 inclusive was 56,543 see Figures 4 and 5. It is notable that there was a peak in May 2024 due to the Second Wind Value Conference. There was also a peak in November 2024, possibly due to a visit to the Wind Energy Ireland Trade Show and attendance at the SSE Roundtable or due to other factors.

Wind Value

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[About Wind Value](#)
[Research Team](#)
[Research Output](#)
[First Conference – Cork 2022](#)
[Wave and Wind Energy Day – Donegal 2023](#)
[Industry Meets Academia Summer Seminar – Cork 2023](#)
[Second Conference – Cork 2024](#)
[SDG2 Challenge Workshop – Tanzania 2024](#)

Striped Wind Turbines are Easier for Birds to Recognize

December 27, 2024

Report by [Sanusha S.](#) in Eco News

Figure 3: Screenshot of Wind Value Website in December 2024

Figure 4: Bar Chart of Website Activity from Feb 2024 to Jan 2025

4 Conclusion

The website is a success attracting a great number of visitors. This may be helped by constant updating of the blog aspect of the site. The social media outreach and the website are exceeding their targets. The previous report, D 1.2, suggested that other channels for social media could be used. LinkedIn has been used and has proven to be very useful. Other social media channels may be considered in the next year.

References

- [1] D. Mikindani, J. O'Brien, P. Leahy, and P. Deeney, "The financial risks from wind turbine failures: a value at risk approach," *Applied Economics*, 2024, cited by: 0; All Open Access, Hybrid Gold Open Access. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85199313442&doi=10.1080%2f00036846.2024.2380542&partnerID=40&md5=79f105ddf8fd7697e05211ac8f112ac9>

Summary by Month										
Month	Daily Avg					Monthly Totals				
	Hits	Files	Pages	Visits	Sites	KBytes	Visits	Pages	Files	Hits
Jan 2025	834	748	574	305	2069	1416226	6100	11483	14972	16681
Dec 2024	656	590	495	250	2597	1314944	7770	15347	18308	20345
Nov 2024	1063	946	835	268	2918	1250154	8063	25076	28385	31899
Oct 2024	723	661	384	226	3078	1323278	7029	11927	20515	22420
Sep 2024	798	732	556	202	3279	1240490	6062	16708	21962	23965
Aug 2024	508	466	356	184	3345	425392	5730	11061	14469	15772
Jul 2024	528	477	318	147	3054	508122	4574	9888	14790	16398
Jun 2024	430	389	191	122	2284	639834	3669	5737	11671	12918
May 2024	923	850	284	146	3051	1182104	4538	8808	26354	28621
Apr 2024	508	420	223	119	2062	497958	3598	6716	12616	15260
Mar 2024	363	304	182	96	1586	413668	3005	5644	9428	11278
Feb 2024	357	317	175	86	1590	444514	2505	5075	9200	10365
Totals						10656684	62643	133470	202670	225922

Figure 5: Table of Website Activity from Feb 2024 to Jan 2025